

Benchmarking deep neural representations for synthetic data evaluation

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ABSTRACT

Robust and accurate evaluation metrics are crucial to test generative models and ensure their practical utility. However, the most common metrics heavily rely on the selected data representation and may not be strongly correlated with the ground truth, which itself can be difficult to obtain. This paper attempts to simplify this process by proposing a benchmark to compare data representations in an automatic manner, i.e. without relying on human evaluators. This is achieved through a simple test based on the assumption that samples with higher quality should lead to improved metric scores. Furthermore, we apply this benchmark on small, low-resolution image datasets to explore various representations, including embeddings finetuned either on the same dataset or on different datasets. An extensive evaluation shows the superiority of pretrained embeddings over randomly initialized representations, as well as evidence that embeddings trained on external, more diverse datasets outperform task-specific ones.

1. Introduction

Over the last decade, deep generative models have been developed and significantly improved. These models have revolutionized our way of working and are increasingly being integrated into our everyday activities (Farina & Lavazza, 2023). While these models are being developed, there is also a growing need to improve the metrics used to evaluate them (Naeem et al., 2020).

The evaluation of generative models can be done using two major approaches, through qualitative or quantitative assessment. Qualitative assessment usually consists of human evaluation through visual inspection of the generated samples (Sajjadi et al., 2018; Theis et al., 2015). Regarding quantitative assessment, there are at least three dimensions which can be evaluated: fidelity, diversity, and generalization. While fidelity assesses the realism of synthetic samples, diversity covers the extent to which these samples represent the variability of real dataset, and generalization measures the degree to which a generative model copies the training data (Alaa et al., 2022).

Common metrics used to evaluate generative models are statistical divergence metrics which quantify how much the real and synthetic distributions differ. Some examples of these metrics are the Fréchet distance, Kullback–Leibler divergence and Maximum Mean Discrepancy (Betzalel et al., 2022). As these statistical analyses are challenging for high-dimensional data, evaluation metrics are often computed based on simpler representations. For that purpose, embedding spaces of pretrained networks can be used to extract low-dimensional representations, as done by Heusel et al. (2018). This work resulted in a

widely used evaluation metric for image generation, Fréchet Inception Distance (FID) (Heusel et al., 2018), which fits Gaussian distributions to feature vectors obtained from the InceptionV3 model (Szegedy et al., 2016) and computes the Fréchet distance between them.

However, these metrics entangle fidelity and diversity into a single value (Alaa et al., 2022). In order to disentangle fidelity and diversity, a definition of precision and recall for distributions was proposed by Sajjadi et al. (2018). Precision evaluates the fidelity, whereas recall evaluates diversity. Both are formulated using relative probability densities of two distributions, modeling a continuum of precision/recall values. However, as their algorithm depends on relative densities, it is unable to provide consistent estimations for the extremes (Kynkäänniemi et al., 2019).

To overcome this challenge, Kynkäänniemi et al. (2019) proposed an improved approach to compute precision and recall, where non-parametric representations (i.e. hyperspheres) are built by calculating pairwise euclidean distances between feature vectors. Despite its advantages, this approach is still vulnerable to outliers and computationally inefficient (Naeem et al., 2020).

Naeem et al. (2020) built upon the work of Kynkäänniemi et al. (2019) and proposed density and coverage to replace, respectively, precision and recall. Density consists on the number of neighborhood spheres centered on real samples that contain a synthetic sample. Coverage is the portion of real samples having at least a synthetic sample within their neighborhoods.

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Table 1

Comparison of related studies. The “Emb. Dataset” column indicates whether the dataset used to train each embedding is treated as a variable in the study. The “General” column denotes whether the method is directly applicable beyond image data. “RI” stands for Random Initialization. “GT” stands for Ground Truth (e.g., human evaluation).

Study	Metrics	Emb. architectures	Emb. Dataset	Automated	General
Betzalel et al. (2022)	8 (statistical divergence)	2	No	Yes	Yes
Lee et al. (2023)	Fréchet distance	5 (incl. RI)	No	Yes	Yes (if adapted)
Kabra and Balakrishnan (2024)	Fréchet distance	4	Yes (for SwaV)	Yes	No (faces)
Yang et al. (2023)	FD and CKA (statistical divergence)	12	No	No (human eval)	Yes (with GT)
Stein et al. (2023)	7 (statistical divergence, disentangled)	8	No	No (human eval)	Yes (with GT)
Ours (this paper)	Density (disentangled)	5 (incl. RI)	Yes	Yes	Yes (if adapted)

Despite these advancements, current metrics rely heavily on the data representations they receive as input (Betzalel et al., 2022; Stein et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2023). Yang et al. (2023) explored different neural network architectures and proposed the use of Centered Kernel Alignment as an alternative to Fréchet distance. Kabra and Balakrishnan (2024) conducted an extensive comparison of Fréchet distances computed across several deep feature representations, demonstrating how these metrics vary when evaluated on synthetic datasets composed of counterfactual face attributes. Betzalel et al. (2022) compared several metrics and two different architectures — CLIP (Radford et al., 2021) and InceptionV3. They concluded that CLIP representations outperform InceptionV3 representations, and showed that metrics such as FID_{∞} (Chong & Forsyth, 2020), Kernel Inception Distance (KID) (Bińkowski et al., 2021) and Clean-FID (Parmar et al., 2022) are better alternatives than the standard FID metric.

Naeem et al. (2020) showed that random embeddings can be a suitable alternative to pretrained embeddings, being able to avoid failure cases when the target dataset is significantly different from the pretraining dataset. Lee et al. (2023) compared randomly initialized representations with features extracted from trained models across several neural network architectures. They concluded that the embeddings from both approaches are complementary, as randomly initialized representations are more sensitive to low-level attributes (e.g., color and texture), whereas trained representations predominantly capture higher-level, class-specific information. We expand upon this exploration of random embeddings by including them in our benchmark, enabling a more direct comparison across various types of representations.

Stein et al. (2023) proposed a large-scale study, comparing several metrics and model architectures. They observed that, when using InceptionV3 embeddings, none of the metrics were strongly correlated with the opinion of human evaluators. After attempting architectures based on vision transformers (Dosovitskiy et al., 2020), much stronger correlations were observed. This points to the importance of studying neural architectures for generative model evaluation. Our work adds to this study by automating the evaluation process instead of relying on human evaluators. We also train our representations on various datasets, adding another dimension to the experiments.

Our study is, to the best of our knowledge, the first to automatically measure the effectiveness of different types of data representations, including random and finetuned embeddings, for synthetic data evaluation (see Table 1). For that purpose, we develop a benchmark to compare data representations across various model architectures, task datasets, and embedding datasets, eliminating the need for human evaluation. We then leverage our benchmark to derive several insights that can help practitioners select the most promising representations.

2. Methodology

In this work, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) and metrics for synthetic data evaluation are used to compare different repre-

Table 2

Selected datasets and their properties. “# Train” and “# Test” correspond to the number of samples in the train and test sets, respectively. “Div. Rank” is the average rank of our diversity measure (lower values mean higher diversity).

Dataset name	Purpose	# Train	# Test	Channels	Div. Rank
Caltech-256	Embedding	24,148	6037	3	1.4
CIFAR-100	Embedding	50,000	10,000	3	2.2
Imagenette	Embedding	9469	3925	3	3.0
CIFAR-10	Task	50,000	10,000	3	3.6
STL-10	Embedding	5000	8000	3	5.0
SVHN	Task	73,257	26,032	3	5.8
KMNIST	Task	60,000	10,000	1	7.6
Fashion-MNIST	Task	60,000	10,000	1	7.8
MNIST	Task	60,000	10,000	1	8.6

sentations over several architectures and datasets.¹ Fig. 1 summarizes our approach, where each representation (i.e. embedding) is tested according to a metric that is applied in 4 different settings: Noise, Weak GAN, GAN and Real. Code is available as a supplementary material.

2.1. Datasets

For our experiments, nine popular image datasets were selected. To homogenize the datasets, all the images were resized to 32×32 . Table 2 shows the selected datasets and their properties. As our main task depends on generative models, our GAN architecture was trained on these datasets without any changes in hyperparameters, having converged for CIFAR-10, SVHN, MNIST, Fashion-MNIST, and KMNIST, all of which have 10 classes. The remaining datasets were used to obtain data representations, in an attempt to compare them with ImageNet and random initialization. Diversity ranks were obtained by first transforming the data into a two-dimensional space using PCA, followed by computing the area covered by the inliers (95%).

2.2. Models

By passing the input data through a neural network, representations can be obtained from the outputs of one or more intermediate layers. These representations, also known as embeddings, can encode information from unstructured data of various modalities (i.e. images, audio, text). When dealing with images, one of the most popular kinds of embeddings used to evaluate generative models are embeddings from models pretrained on ImageNet (Kynkäänniemi et al., 2019; Naeem et al., 2020; Sajjadi et al., 2018). In this work, we finetune these baseline ImageNet embeddings on different datasets and compare their

¹ In this work, the term “synthetic data evaluation” specifically refers to the assessment of synthetic image datasets. However, the proposed benchmark is generic and applicable to any data modality that can be encoded into a suitable representation (usually via a neural network).

Fig. 1. Scheme of our approach. “Model” corresponds to the model used to compute data representations (i.e. embeddings). The embedding dataset may coincide with the task dataset.

Table 3
Summary of model parameters and computational complexity.

Model	Parameters (M)	GFLOPS
MobileNetV2 (Sandler et al., 2018)	2.5	0.06
GoogLeNet (Szegedy et al., 2015)	6.62	1.5
EfficientNetB0 (Tan & Le, 2019)	5.29	0.39
EfficientNetB3 (Tan & Le, 2019)	12.23	1.83
ConvNext-Tiny (Liu et al., 2022)	28.59	4.46
ResNet18 (He et al., 2016)	11.69	1.81
GAN Critic (Arjovsky et al., 2017)	1.23	0.034

performance. We also include randomly initialized embeddings in the comparison. These experiments are performed for several architectures, shown in Table 3. Models were downloaded from the official pytorch repository (Paszke et al., 2019). We chose the ones that were able to process 32×32 images directly, without the need to increase their resolution. InceptionV3, despite being a popular embedding architecture, requires resizing the images to a larger resolution, so we chose GoogLeNet (i.e. InceptionV1) (Szegedy et al., 2015) as an alternative. Additionally, we used the critic portion of our GANs as a baseline embedding model with no additional training costs.

The generative model architecture used for our experiments was a conditional Wasserstein GAN with gradient penalty (Gulrajani et al., 2017). It consists of a generator and a critic that are trained by minimizing an approximation of the Wasserstein distance (Arjovsky et al., 2017).

2.3. Metrics-based testing

To compare the embeddings, we propose a test in which the values of a given metric (M) should follow a specific order:

$$M(\text{Noise}, \text{Test}) \leq M(\text{Weak GAN}, \text{Test}) \leq M(\text{GAN}, \text{Test}) \leq M(\text{Real}, \text{Test}), \quad (1)$$

where “Real” and “Test” are subsets randomly sampled from the train and test sets, respectively. “GAN” is our Wasserstein GAN with gradient

penalty trained on the train set. “Weak GAN” is the same GAN model, but with its training stopped after 5 epochs. “Noise” is a set of images produced by sampling random values from a uniform distribution.

This assumption allows us to compare the representations in a systematic manner and based on their practical usefulness. In practice, we split this comparison into its three pairwise components to enable more fine-grained scoring, as a representation that satisfies two out of three inequalities should be considered more valuable than one that satisfies none. This performance metric is given as a percentage and is referred to as “% Passed” in Section 3.

In addition to the percentage of passed tests, the average rank was chosen as a function to aggregate the test results, since it compares the performance of each embedding against the others, complementing the evaluation. The average rank is given by:

$$\text{Average Rank}(e) = \frac{1}{|D||A|} \sum_{d \in D} \sum_{a \in A} \text{Rank}(e, d, a) \quad (2)$$

where e is a specific embedding, D is the set of task datasets, A is the set of model architectures, and $\text{Rank}(e, d, a)$ denotes the rank of embedding e for dataset d and architecture a . To preserve information, the average ranks are computed separately for each combination of task dataset and architecture.

From our preliminary experiments, statistical divergence metrics such as the Fréchet distance usually considered $M(\text{Noise}, \text{Test})$ as being larger than $M(\text{Weak GAN}, \text{Test})$, which is arguably undesirable for most real-world tasks, as a weak GAN is expected to produce some samples with more structure than random noise. This may be due to the inherent problem of statistical divergence metrics, which entangle fidelity and diversity (Kynkäänniemi et al., 2019). Our tests attempt to compare the fidelity of generative models, which is a measurement of their ability to produce samples that lie in the training data distribution. Consequently, Density (Naeem et al., 2020) and Precision (Kynkäänniemi et al., 2019) were chosen as our main metrics, since their purpose is to compute the fidelity of the generated samples.

2.4. Experimental setup

Our benchmark (Fig. 1 and Algorithm 1) starts by looping over all the datasets and 6 hyperparameter combinations. Our generative

Fig. 2. Samples from each task dataset and setting, except for the “Noise” setting.

models are trained inside this loop, along with the creation of 10 000 samples in our four settings (Noise, Weak GAN, GAN, and Real). An inner loop over the datasets is applied with the purpose of finetuning every combination of task dataset, embedding dataset, and architecture for each hyperparameter setting. Subsequently, Density and Precision are computed for all the pairwise comparisons of sample sets. Finally, our performance scores are computed based on the number of pairwise comparisons (up to a maximum of 3) that are verified over all hyperparameter combinations, obtaining 18 possible scores per combination of task dataset, type of embedding, and model architecture. See Section 2.3 for more details.

Our representations were extracted from a model that was either randomly initialized, finetuned on the task dataset, or finetuned on an external dataset, i.e. any dataset that is not the task dataset. Every experiment was performed over 6 combinations of two optimizers (Adam Kingma & Ba, 2014 and AdamW Loshchilov & Hutter, 2017) and three learning rates (0.0005, 0.001, and 0.005), with a different random seed for each combination. Batch size was fixed to 128. The datasets selected for our tasks were CIFAR-10, SVHN, MNIST, Fashion-MNIST, and KMNIST. Our GAN models were trained over the same 6 random seeds using Adam optimizer and a learning rate of 0.0001. While Weak GAN was only trained for 5 epochs, all the remaining models were trained for a maximum of 200 epochs with early stopping after 20 epochs without improvement. Fig. 2 shows sample images for each task dataset for the Weak GAN, GAN, and Real settings.

3. Results

3.1. Embedding datasets

Table 4 shows the performance of each embedding dataset. Despite ImageNet embeddings having slightly outperformed the remaining approaches, the performance achieved by Caltech-256 and CIFAR-100 finetuning was not significantly different, with the advantage of being much smaller datasets. Overall, task embeddings were outperformed by all the embeddings trained on external datasets, possibly due to the added bias in evaluating the representations on their training dataset. Embeddings from randomly initialized models were the worst performing representations. Still, they may be a promising approach for tasks where there are no pretrained models available. Interestingly, the

Algorithm 1 Data Representation Benchmark

Require: Task datasets D_{task} , Embedding datasets D_{embed} , Embedding Architectures E , GAN Architecture G , Metric M , Hyperparameter settings H

- 1: **for all** $d_{\text{task}} \in D_{\text{task}}$ **do**
- 2: **for all** $h \in H$ **do**
- 3: Train GAN $G_{d_{\text{task}}}$ on d_{task} using h : WeakGAN (5 epochs) and GAN (converged)
- 4: Generate four sample sets: Noise, WeakGAN, GAN, Real
- 5: **for all** $d_{\text{embed}} \in D_{\text{embed}}$ **do**
- 6: **for all** $e \in E$ **do**
- 7: Finetune e on d_{embed} using h (except if random init)
- 8: Extract features for each sample set via e
- 9: Compute:
- 10: $m_1 = M(\text{Noise}, \text{Real})$
- 11: $m_2 = M(\text{WeakGAN}, \text{Real})$
- 12: $m_3 = M(\text{GAN}, \text{Real})$
- 13: Count passes $p_{e,d_{\text{task}},d_{\text{embed}},h} = \sum_{i=1}^3 [m_{i-1} \leq m_i]$ ▷
- 14: Eq. 1
- 15: **end for**
- 16: **end for**
- 17: **end for**
- 18: Compute “% Passed” and Average Rank ▷ Eq. 2
- 19: **return** Ranked Embeddings and Architectures

Table 4

Performance for each embedding dataset. “Task” embeddings are extracted from models trained on the task dataset. “Random” indicates embeddings from randomly initialized models. “% Passed” indicates the average percentage of passed tests. “(D)” and “(P)” stand for Density and Precision, respectively.

Embedding	% Passed (D) (↑) ^a	Avg. rank (D) (↓)	Avg. rank (P) (↓)
ImageNet	96.67 ± 4.28	3.25	3.33
Caltech-256	97.14 ± 3.40	3.30	3.33
CIFAR-100	96.83 ± 3.38	3.31	3.39
Imagenette	95.71 ± 4.28	3.66	3.64
STL-10	94.92 ± 5.11	4.01*	4.01
Task	88.57 ± 12.49	4.61**	4.49**
Random	85.37 ± 13.17	5.20***	5.17***

* Significance level: $p < 0.05$.

** Significance level: $p < 0.01$.

*** Significance level: $p < 0.001$.

^a “% Passed” for Precision, being nearly identical to Density, was omitted to optimize formatting.

embeddings that perform best after ImageNet are the four most diverse external datasets in the same order (see Table 2). This is consistent with several findings in the literature (Betzael et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2023).

3.2. Embedding architectures

Table 5 shows the overall performance of each architecture used to extract representations. The Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used once again to obtain the pairwise p-values between each embedding architecture and the reference architecture with the lowest rank (GAN Critic). We consider average rank to be more reliable than “% passed”, since ranks were first computed separately for each pair of task dataset and embedding before being averaged. In this case, performance was not clearly influenced by any of the model properties described in Section 2.2, as the largest model, ConvNext-Tiny, had the worst performance, while the second largest, EfficientNetB3, placed fourth in terms of performance. GoogLeNet and ResNet18, the best performing models aside from the GAN Critic, may have other desirable attributes which make them more suitable for evaluating. Nonetheless, we could not find

Table 5

Performance of the selected embedding architectures. “% Passed” indicates the average percentage of passed tests. “(D)” and “(P)” stand for Density and Precision, respectively.

Architecture	% Passed (D)(†) ^a	Avg. rank (D)(↓)	Avg. rank (P)(↓)
GAN Critic	97.78 ± 2.78	3.10	3.18
GoogLeNet	95.56 ± 6.57	3.27	3.24
ResNet18	94.76 ± 6.59	3.54*	3.54*
EfficientNetB3	92.86 ± 9.00	3.97*	4.09*
EfficientNetB0	93.17 ± 8.64	4.09**	4.19**
MobileNetV2	92.22 ± 9.55	4.36**	4.27**
ConvNext-Tiny	90.79 ± 11.97	4.56***	4.40**

* Significance level: $p < 0.05$.

** Significance level: $p < 0.01$.

*** Significance level: $p < 0.001$.

^a “% Passed” for Precision, being nearly identical to Density, was omitted to optimize formatting.

strong correlations with other properties such as task accuracy, weight norm ($\|W\|_2$), and Hessian matrix statistics.

While the GAN Critic was our best performing embedding model, this result may not be generalizable, since it was computed by pre-trained GANs from different seeds on the same datasets, which may be biased, as our tests depend on very similar GAN models. However, if GANs are trained to generate data, their representations could potentially be helpful for evaluation.

4. Discussion

In practice, our automatic approach to compare data representations could potentially thrive in cases where the ground truth for data quality is difficult to obtain. For example, for medical data, rigorous visual inspection of synthetic samples could be very costly, as it would require experts with considerable experience. Additionally, computing fidelity metrics using reliable representations could help reduce the labeling effort by preselecting the most relevant samples for experts to evaluate.

Our results showed that embeddings trained on external datasets, such as those from ImageNet, achieved an average rank of 3.25, which was statistically superior ($p < 0.01$) to the ranks achieved STL-10, task-specific embeddings (4.61) and randomly initialized representations (5.20, $p < 0.001$). These results confirm the robustness of our benchmark, showing potential for the practical usefulness of our method.

As an alternative to finetuning the embedding models, training them from scratch while keeping the hyperparameters constant across seeds and datasets could minimize possible biases associated with knowledge retention from ImageNet. However, while attempting this approach, some models did not achieve an acceptable performance after training. Despite that, ImageNet-pretrained models without finetuning still outperformed finetuning on each of the remaining datasets.

Concerning the embedding architectures, the GAN Critic achieved the best performance with an average rank of 3.10, it was statistically superior to all the remaining architectures, yet, it was on par with GoogLeNet, which has a relatively small number of parameters (6.62 M). This indicates that larger neural networks do not necessarily produce more discriminative embeddings.

Regarding the use of the GAN critic as an embedding model, a potential reason for its success could be related to the fact that its training objective is to separate real from synthetic samples, which could have led to more calibrated representations that may have helped in our test cases. Still, further research is needed to better understand this phenomenon.

The performance results were virtually the same for Density and Precision. This suggests that our benchmark may be robust to different fidelity metrics.

The ImageNet dataset and the GoogLeNet (Inception-v1) architecture achieved the best and second-best results, respectively. Curiously, this coincides with standard metrics such as Inception score

(IS) and Fréchet Inception Distance (FID), whose feature extractors are Inception models trained on ImageNet (typically Inception-v3).

An apparent limitation of our approach is that it was specifically developed and validated for image data. Nevertheless, a similar methodology could be extended to other data modalities, provided that suitable model architectures and tests are adapted accordingly.

Another limitation of our approach is that our test relies on three conditions that may not be true for all the generated samples. Specifically, we assume that real samples are of higher quality than those generated by a fully trained GAN, which in turn outperform samples from a partially trained GAN and, lastly, random noise. While this ordering is intuitive and aligns with standard expectations, it is still an approximation. In particular, the inclusion of a partially trained GAN (after 5 epochs) was intended to introduce an intermediate quality level for a more precise comparison. Although individual samples may occasionally violate this order, on average, our ranking holds and is able to provide a practical framework for systematically comparing data representations.

Future work could focus on devising tests with more robust conditions. For example, a test set for data representations could include a set of validated samples for a certain number of quality levels. Furthermore, a comparison with human perceptual ratings would provide additional validation to our benchmark.

We summarize our findings below:

- While randomly initialized representations can be suitable for evaluating generative models, pretrained models generally perform better;
- Representations trained on external datasets typically outperform those trained on the dataset corresponding to the current task;
- Representations trained on more diverse datasets often achieve better performance;
- Larger architectures do not necessarily lead to improved representations;
- The critic portion of a GAN can potentially be used as an embedding model.

5. Conclusion

This study proposed a method to compare data representations for synthetic data evaluation in an automatic manner. Based on this method, a benchmark was implemented and several experiments were performed by combining different datasets, types of embeddings, and embedding model architectures.

While some insights were derived from these experiments, similar studies would be beneficial, preferably at larger scales. These studies could explore different data modalities, image resolutions, metrics, representation formats, architectures (e.g., vision transformers), generative models (e.g., diffusion models), datasets, and a wider range of hyperparameters.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Nuno Bento: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Joana Rebelo:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Marília Barandas:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iswa.2025.200580>.

Data availability

All datasets used are publicly available.

References

- Alaa, A., Van Breugel, B., Saveliev, E. S., & van der Schaar, M. (2022). How faithful is your synthetic data? Sample-level metrics for evaluating and auditing generative models. In K. Chaudhuri, S. Jegelka, L. Song, C. Szepesvari, G. Niu, & S. Sabato (Eds.), *Proceedings of machine learning research: vol. 162, Proceedings of the 39th international conference on machine learning* (pp. 290–306). PMLR.
- Arjovsky, M., Chintala, S., & Bottou, L. (2017). Wasserstein gan. arXiv preprint arXiv:1701.07875.
- Betzalel, E., Penso, C., Navon, A., & Fetaya, E. (2022). A study on the evaluation of generative models. arXiv preprint arXiv:2206.10935.
- Bińkowski, M., Sutherland, D. J., Arbel, M., & Gretton, A. (2021). Demystifying MMD GANs.
- Chong, M. J., & Forsyth, D. (2020). Effectively unbiased fid and inception score and where to find them. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* (pp. 6070–6079).
- Dosovitskiy, A., Beyer, L., Kolesnikov, A., Weissenborn, D., Zhai, X., Unterthiner, T., Dehghani, M., Minderer, M., Heigold, G., Gelly, S., et al. (2020). An image is worth 16x16 words: Transformers for image recognition at scale. arXiv preprint arXiv:2010.11929.
- Farina, M., & Lavazza, A. (2023). ChatGPT in society: Emerging issues. *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence*, 6, Article 1130913.
- Gulrajani, I., Ahmed, F., Arjovsky, M., Dumoulin, V., & Courville, A. C. (2017). Improved training of wasserstein gans. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 30.
- He, K., Zhang, X., Ren, S., & Sun, J. (2016). Deep residual learning for image recognition. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* (pp. 770–778).
- Heusel, M., Ramsauer, H., Unterthiner, T., Nessler, B., & Hochreiter, S. (2018). GANs trained by a two time-scale update rule converge to a local Nash equilibrium.
- Kabra, K., & Balakrishnan, G. (2024). F? D: On understanding the role of deep feature spaces on face generation evaluation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* (pp. 8327–8332).
- Kingma, D. P., & Ba, J. (2014). Adam: A method for stochastic optimization. arXiv preprint arXiv:1412.6980.
- Kynkäänniemi, T., Karras, T., Laine, S., Lehtinen, J., & Aila, T. (2019). Improved precision and recall metric for assessing generative models.
- Lee, J., Kim, J.-H., & Lee, J.-S. (2023). Demystifying randomly initialized networks for evaluating generative models. vol. 37, In *Proceedings of the AAAI conference on artificial intelligence* (pp. 8482–8490). 7.
- Liu, Z., Mao, H., Wu, C.-Y., Feichtenhofer, C., Darrell, T., & Xie, S. (2022). A convnet for the 2020s. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* (pp. 11976–11986).
- Loshchilov, I., & Hutter, F. (2017). Decoupled weight decay regularization. arXiv preprint arXiv:1711.05101.
- Naem, M. F., Oh, S. J., Uh, Y., Choi, Y., & Yoo, J. (2020). Reliable fidelity and diversity metrics for generative models.
- Parmar, G., Zhang, R., & Zhu, J.-Y. (2022). On aliased resizing and surprising subtleties in gan evaluation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* (pp. 11410–11420).
- Paszke, A., Gross, S., Massa, F., Lerer, A., Bradbury, J., Chanan, G., Killeen, T., Lin, Z., Gimelshein, N., Antiga, L., et al. (2019). Pytorch: An imperative style, high-performance deep learning library. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 32.
- Radford, A., Kim, J. W., Hallacy, C., Ramesh, A., Goh, G., Agarwal, S., Sastry, G., Askell, A., Mishkin, P., Clark, J., et al. (2021). Learning transferable visual models from natural language supervision. In *International conference on machine learning* (pp. 8748–8763). PMLR.
- Sajjadi, M. S. M., Bachem, O., Lucic, M., Bousquet, O., & Gelly, S. (2018). Assessing generative models via precision and recall.
- Sandler, M., Howard, A., Zhu, M., Zhmoginov, A., & Chen, L.-C. (2018). Mobilenetv2: Inverted residuals and linear bottlenecks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* (pp. 4510–4520).
- Stein, G., Cresswell, J., Hosseinzadeh, R., Sui, Y., Ross, B., Villetcroze, V., Liu, Z., Caterini, A. L., Taylor, E., & Loaiza-Ganem, G. (2023). Exposing flaws of generative model evaluation metrics and their unfair treatment of diffusion models. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 36, 3732–3784.
- Szegedy, C., Liu, W., Jia, Y., Sermanet, P., Reed, S., Anguelov, D., Erhan, D., Vanhoucke, V., & Rabinovich, A. (2015). Going deeper with convolutions. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* (pp. 1–9).
- Szegedy, C., Vanhoucke, V., Ioffe, S., Shlens, J., & Wojna, Z. (2016). Rethinking the inception architecture for computer vision. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* (pp. 2818–2826).
- Tan, M., & Le, Q. (2019). Efficientnet: Rethinking model scaling for convolutional neural networks. In *International conference on machine learning* (pp. 6105–6114). PMLR.
- Theis, L., Oord, A. v. d., & Bethge, M. (2015). A note on the evaluation of generative models. arXiv preprint arXiv:1511.01844.
- Yang, C., Zhang, Y., Bai, Q., Shen, Y., Dai, B., et al. (2023). Revisiting the evaluation of image synthesis with GANs. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 36, 9518–9542.